

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D4.6 FAIR Data Cubes - Release III

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Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management
AERONET	AERosol RObotic NETwork
AOD	Aerosol Optical Thickness
API	Application Programming Language
AVIRIS	Airborne Visible/InfraRed Imaging Spectrometer
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CARRA	C3S Arctic Regional Reanalysis
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CNR	National Council of Research
DAS	Data Access System
DIAS	Data and Information Access Service
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ER-2	Earth Resources-2
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reproducible
INGV	National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology
LST	Land Surface Temperature
MEE0	Meteorological and Environmental Earth Observation
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Agency
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
NWS	National Weather Service
RELIANCE	Research Lifecycle Management technologies for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC
RO	Research Object
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
UERRA	Uncertainties in Ensembles of Regional Reanalyses
UiO	University of Oslo
UTC	Universal Time Clock
VIIRS	Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WMS	Web Map Service
WOA	World Ocean Atlas

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1 Executive Summary

RELIANCE, short for *Research Lifecycle Management for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*, aims to realize the vision of FAIR research in EOSC by adopting a holistic research management approach based on three key and complementary technologies: i) Research objects (RO) as the overarching mechanism to manage scientific research activities; ii) data cubes as the mechanisms enabling an efficient and scalable Earth Observation data discovery and access; iii) text mining and semantic enrichment services allowing to extract machine-readable metadata from RO resources, enabling researchers to discover scientific information at scale and to structure their own research.

This document describes the final release of FAIR Data Cube resources requested by RELIANCE user communities and made available within the RELIANCE project. The FAIR Data Cube resources are stored in the MEEO cloud resources.

The Data Cube Metadata Model adopted for describing FAIR Data Cubes and Data Cube API are detailed in the D4.1 and D4.2, respectively.

2 Introduction

This document is an update of the D4.4 “FAIR Data Cubes - Release I” and D4.5 “FAIR Data Cubes - Release II”: it gives the updated list of data cubes resources at month 21 (see Section 3) as requested by the RELIANCE user communities.

In particular the following datacube resources have been added:

- World Ocean Atlas 2018 - Temperature and Salinity at different temporal resolutions (see Table 2);
- MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA – MOD/MYD03 - Geolocation - 1km (see Table 13);
- Sentinel-3 Aerosol Optical Depth (see Table 20);
- Sentinel-3 Top of Atmosphere Radiances and Brightness Temperature (see Table 21);
- TDM90 Elevation (see Table 22);
- SRTM XSAR Digital Elevation Model (see Table 23);
- ERA5-Land hourly data from 1981 to present (see Table 27).

The release plan (see Table 1) is also updated to keep into consideration the user feedback, new dataset requirements and technical deviations mainly due to data collection from external archives.

2.1 Data Cubes

The concept of Data Cube applied to geospatial data has progressively gathered more and more consensus as an effective technology to support the uptake of satellite EO applications. In the international scenario, Data Cubes are being progressively adopted at national level to provide a common reference and data access infrastructure for geospatial data, mostly related to the access and exploitation of large collections of multi-temporal, multi-resolution satellite imagery. Data Cube technology is rapidly evolving thanks to the parallel evolution of data storage systems (e.g., the progressive affirmation of object storage in cloud environments), databases and elastic and scalable computing capacities.

Although the definition of Data Cube is still missing, and both users' communities and standardization bodies (e.g., Open Geospatial Consortium) are working on it, Data Cubes are widely considered as a technological enabler providing efficient and cost-effective interfaces to access large volumes (and large variety) of geospatial data (EO and non-EO).

A Data Cube is generally represented as a multi-dimensional data concept (which can be 1-dimensional, 2-dimensional, 3-dimensional, or higher-dimensional), but more in general a Data Cube consists of a comprehensive set of functions that describe the digital resources. While the detailed definition of the FAIR Data Cube metadata model [D4.1], the Data Cube services need to describe both the data structure (e.g., its spatial resolution or temporal dimensions and granularity), to all the available services to exploit discovery, access, view and analytics services.

The ADAM platform is used as reference implementation of Data Cube to enable access to geospatial data requested by the RELIANCE user communities including Sea Monitoring represented by CNR-ISMAR, Geohazard represented by INGV, and Atmospheric and climate modelling represented by the University of OSLO.

In order to integrate the FAIR Data Cube services in the European Open Science Cloud infrastructure, and to guarantee a high level of interoperability and reusability of Copernicus and non-Copernicus data, the harmonization and alignment with ongoing OGC Testbed17 activities¹ is also pursued.

2.2 ADAM platform

The Advanced geospatial Data Management platform (ADAM) is a tool to access a large variety and volume of global environmental data. ADAM allows you to extract global as well as local data, from the past, current time, as well as short term forecast and long-term projections. Most of the data are updated daily bringing users the most recent data to play with.

In the framework of RELIANCE project activities, an instance of ADAM is deployed and configured to access Copernicus and non-Copernicus satellite- and model-based data.

2.2.1 Principles and architecture

The core of ADAM is a Data Access System (DAS), a software module that manages a large variety of geospatial information that feature different data formats, geographic / geometric and time resolution. It allows accessing, visualizing, sub-setting, combining, processing, downloading all data sources simultaneously. The DAS exposes OGC Open Search and Web Coverage Service (WCS 2.x) interfaces that allow discovering available datasets and subset them in any dimension with a single query (see figure below).

¹ <https://www.ogc.org/projects/initiatives/t17>

Figure 1. ADAM Data Access System (DAS) module

ADAM is a very modular platform: various DAS are deployed on different data sources (DIAS Mundi, DIAS CREODIAS, Amazon Web Services - AWS, MEEO Data Facility), allowing accessing and sub-setting the available datasets without downloading / duplicating the data. Distributed data sources are made accessible through the Data Cube layer, that exposes OGC-standardised interfaces. On top of the Data Cube layer, platform-based interfaces (web application, mobile application, Jupyter Notebook and APIs) as well as third party user interfaces can be deployed.

Figure 2. ADAM high-level architecture

ADAM, referred also as a virtual Data Cube technology, enables seamless access to all available datasets through a single interface to allow developing user-centred solutions on top of it; cutting the access barriers to a large variety of data (no need to know the exact format of any of the available datasets) it saves data preparation time and facilitates the simultaneous use of data coming from different sources.

2.2.2 Data Cube specifications and indexing

The ADAM platform is designed to support heterogeneous data, including satellite-based, model-based and geospatial datasets. Ad-hoc modules and components allow at handling resources in their native data format both on local and remote infrastructures.

To optimise the data exploitation, especially for web services and applications, it is recommended to generate Analysis-Ready Data (ARD) as Cloud Optimised GeoTIFF (COG) that improve the performances of view services.

Nonetheless, the following specifications are supported:

- Data formats: GeoTIFF, nc, HDF, jp2, Cloud Optimised GeoTIFF, ...
- Tiling schema: MGRS (Sentinel-2), WRS-2 (Landsat)
- Projections: UTM, Mercator, Polar, ...

A series of bash and python tools are used to build data cubes, extract metadata and index the data cube resources. In particular, for RELIANCE an internal ADAM python module manages the full process: from data collection, to data pre-processing (e.g., in case the generation of ARD is needed), till to the indexing in the DAS service component.

To extend datacube portfolio and manage unsupported datasets, an existing module is reused and extended or a new module is developed to handle all necessary metadata.

3 RELIANCE Data Cubes

In the framework of the RELIANCE project activities dedicated instances of ADAM Explorer and Data Access System (DAS) are deployed in the MEEO infrastructure, and successfully integrated in the European Open Science Cloud to enable pixel-based access to Copernicus and non-Copernicus satellite-based and model-based data.

The RELIANCE Data Cube service is accessible at: <https://reliance.adamplatform.eu>.

The following table summarizes the Data Cube user requirements gathered by the RELIANCE communities' members belonging to Sea Monitoring represented by CNR-ISMAR, Geohazard represented by INGV, and Atmospheric and climate modelling represented by the University of OSLO. The Data Cube services will optimize the access to the data by offering a seamless and unique interface to the heterogenous datasets (e.g., satellite-based and model-based) and data formats (e.g., tiff, HDF, nc, ...).

The description of the second release of FAIR Data Cube resources follows in Section 3.1.

Table 1 – RELIANCE Data Cubes, including user community and planned release.

Community	Data Cube	Release (Month)
CNR	Ocean Color Data	R1 (M6)
CNR	World Ocean Atlas 2018	R2 (M12)
CNR	Mediterranean Sea Monthly and Daily Interpolated Surface Chlorophyll Concentration from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations	R2 (M12)

CNR	Mediterranean Sea Reprocessed Surface Chlorophyll Concentration and Phytoplankton Functional Types from Multi Satellite observations	R2 (M12)
CNR	Mediterranean Sea Surface Chlorophyll Concentration from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI Observations	R2 (M12)
CNR	Mediterranean Sea Monthly and Daily Reprocessed Surface Chlorophyll Concentration From Multi Satellite Observations + Seawifs Daily Climatology	R2 (M12)
CNR	Mediterranean Sea Monthly Attenuation Coefficient at 490nm from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI Observations	R2 (M12)
CNR	Mediterranean Sea Remote Sensing Reflectances and Attenuation Coefficient at 490nm from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI Observations	R2 (M12)
CNR	Mediterranean Sea Reprocessed Remote Sensing Reflectances and Attenuation CoefficientaAt 490nm from Multi Satellite Observations	R2 (M12)
INGV	Sentinel-1 Single Look Complex	R3 (M21)
INGV	Sentinel-1 Unwrapped interferograms and coherence maps	R2 (M12)
INGV	Sentinel-3 Land Surface Temperature	R2 (M12)
INGV	Sentinel-3 Aerosol Optical Depth	R3 (M21)
INGV	Sentinel-3 Top of Atmosphere Radiances and Brightness Temperature	R3 (M21)
INGV	Tandem X (DEM 90m)	R2 (M12)
INGV	SRMT (DEM 30 m)	R2 (M12)
INGV	MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA	R1 (M6)
UiO	CAMS European air quality forecasts	R1 (M6)
UiO	UERRA regional reanalysis for Europe on single levels from 1961 to 2019	R2 (M12)
UiO	Arctic regional reanalysis on single levels from 1998 to 2019	R2 (M12)
UiO	ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis	R2 (M21)

3.1 CNR Data Cube resources

Table 2. CNR Data Cube: World Ocean Atlas 2018

Title	Description
Data Cube	World Ocean Atlas 2018
Dataset name [datasetId]	World Ocean Database (WOD) Temperature (monthly,yearly,seasonal) [WOD_MONTHLY_t_an,WOD_ANNUAL_t_an,WOD_SEASONAL_t_an] World Ocean Database (WOD) Salinity (monthly,yearly,seasonal) [WOD_MONTHLY_s_an,WOD_ANNUAL_s_an,WOD_SEASONAL_s_an]
Title	World Ocean Atlas 2018 Temperature/Salinity
Description	World Ocean Atlas 2018 (WOA18) is a set of objectively analyzed (one degree grid and quarter degree grid) climatological fields of in situ temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, Apparent Oxygen Utilization (AOU), percent oxygen saturation, phosphate, silicate, and nitrate at standard depth levels for annual, seasonal, and monthly compositing periods for the World Ocean. Quarter degree fields are for temperature and salinity only. It also includes associated statistical fields of observed oceanographic profile data interpolated to standard depth levels on quarter degree, one degree, and five degree grids. Temperature and salinity fields are available for six decades (1955-1964, 1965-1974, 1975-1984, 1985-1994, 1995-2004, and 2005-2017) an average of all decades representing the period 1955-2017, as well as a thirty year "climate normal" period 1981-2010. Oxygen fields (as well as AOU and percent oxygen saturation) are available using all quality controlled data 1960-2017, nutrient fields using all quality controlled data from the entire sampling period 1878-2017. This accession is a product generated by the National Centers for Environmental

	Information's (NCEI) Ocean Climate Laboratory Team. The analyses are derived from the NCEI World Ocean Database 2018.
Preview	
Area of Interest	Global
Time range	1955-1964, 1965-1974, 1975-1984, 1985-1994, 1995-2004, and 2005-2017

Table 3. CNR Data Cube: Ocean Color Data KD490.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Ocean Color Data
Dataset name [datasetId]	Ocean Color Data: Modis-aqua_KD490 (monthly) [MODh20kd490MO_4km] Ocean Color Data: Modis-aqua_KD490 (yearly) [MODh20kd490YR_4km]
Title	Diffuse attenuation coefficient for downwelling irradiance at 490 nm (Kd_490)
Description	<p>MODIS Diffuse Attenuation Coefficient at 490 nm (Kd490)</p> <p>The diffuse attenuation coefficient in water indicates how strongly light intensity at a specified wavelength is attenuated within the water column. This parameter has wide applicability in ocean optics, as it is directly related to the presence of scattering particles in the water column, either organic or inorganic, and thus is an indication of water clarity.</p> <p>The diffuse attenuation coefficient at 490 nm (Kd490) indicates the turbidity of the water column - how visible light in the blue to green region of the spectrum penetrates within the water column. The value of Kd490 represents the rate which light at 490 nm is attenuated with depth. For example, a Kd490 of 0.1/meter means that light intensity will be reduced one natural log within 10 meters of water. Thus, for a Kd490 of 0.1, one attenuation length is 10 meters. Higher Kd490 value means smaller attenuation depth, and lower clarity of ocean water.</p>
Preview	

Area of Interest	Global
Time range	2002-2018

Table 4. CNR Data Cube: Ocean Color Data CHL_A.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Ocean Color Data
Dataset name [datasetId]	Ocean Color Data: Modis-aqua_chl-a (yearly) [MODh20chlYR_4km] Ocean Color Data: Modis-aqua_chl-a (monthly) [MODh20chlMO_4km]
Title	Chlorophyll a (chlor_a)
Description	<p>This algorithm returns the near-surface concentration of chlorophyll-a (chlor_a) in mg m⁻³, calculated using an empirical relationship derived from in situ measurements of chlor_a and remote sensing reflectance (R_{rs}) in the blue-to-green region of the visible spectrum. The implementation is contingent on the availability of three or more sensor bands spanning the 440 - 670 nm spectral regime. The algorithm is applicable to all current ocean color sensors. The chlor_a product is included as part of the standard Level-2 OC product suite and the Level-3 CHL product suite.</p> <p>The current implementation for the default chlorophyll algorithm (chlor_a) employs the standard OC3/OC4 (OCx) band ratio algorithm merged with the color index (CI) of Hu et al. (2012). As described in that paper, this refinement is restricted to relatively clear water, and the general impact is to reduce artifacts and biases in clear-water chlorophyll retrievals due to residual glint, stray light, atmospheric correction errors, and white or spectrally-linear bias errors in R_{rs}. As implemented, the algorithm diverges slightly from what was published in Hu et al. (2012) in that the transition between CI and OCx now occurs at 0.15 < CI < 0.2 mg/m³ to ensure a smooth transition.</p>
Preview	

Area of Interest	Global
Time range	2002-2018

Table 5. CNR Data Cube: Ocean Color Data Photosynthetically Available Radiation.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Ocean Color Data
Dataset name [datasetId]	MODIS Daily Mean Photosynthetically Available Radiation (yearly) [MODh20PARYR_4km] MODIS Daily Mean Photosynthetically Available Radiation (monthly) [MODh20PARMO_4km]
Title	Photosynthetically Available Radiation (PAR)
Description	<p>MODIS Daily Mean Photosynthetically Available Radiation</p> <p>This algorithm estimates daily average photosynthetically available radiation (PAR) at the ocean surface in Einstein m⁻² d⁻¹. PAR is defined as the quantum energy flux from the Sun in the 400-700nm range. For ocean color applications, PAR is a common input used in modeling marine primary productivity. Implementation of this algorithm is contingent on the availability of observed top-of-atmosphere radiances in the visible spectral regime that do not saturate over clouds. The algorithm is applicable to MODIS, MERIS, SeaWiFS, and VIIRS, but it can be operated on all ocean color sensors. The PAR product is included as part of the standard Level-2 OC product suite and the Level-3 PAR product suite.</p>
Preview	

Area of Interest	Global
Time range	2002-2018

Table 6. CNR Data Cube: Mediterranean Sea Monthly and Daily Interpolated Surface Chlorophyll Concentration from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Mediterranean Sea Monthly and Daily Interpolated Surface Chlorophyll Concentration from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations
Dataset name [datasetId]	Mediterranean Sea Monthly and Daily Interpolated Surface Chlorophyll Concentration from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations [OCMEDCHLNRTL4]
Title	Chlorophyll a (chlor_a)
Description	<p>The Global Ocean Satellite monitoring and marine ecosystem study group (GOS) of the Italian National Research Council (CNR), in Rome, distributes Level-4 product including the daily interpolated chlorophyll field with no data voids starting from the multi-sensor (MODIS-Aqua, NOAA-20-VIIRS, NPP-VIIRS, Sentinel3A-OLCI at 300m of resolution) (at 1 km resolution) and the monthly averaged chlorophyll concentration for the multi-sensor (at 1 km resolution) and Sentinel-OLCI Level-3 (at 300m resolution). Chlorophyll field are obtained by means of the Mediterranean regional algorithms: an updated version of the MedOC4 (Case 1 waters, Volpe et al., 2019, with new coefficients) and AD4 (Case 2 waters, Berthon and Zibordi, 2004). Discrimination between the two water types is performed by comparing the satellite spectrum with the average water type spectral signature from in situ measurements for both water types. Reference insitu dataset is MedBiOp (Volpe et al., 2019) where pure Case II spectra are selected using a k-mean cluster analysis (Melin et al., 2015). Merging of Case I and Case II information is performed estimating the Mahalanobis distance between the observed and reference spectra and using it as weight for the final merged value. The interpolated gap-free Level-4 Chl concentration is estimated by means of a modified version of the DINEOF algorithm by GOS (Volpe et al., 2018). DINEOF is an iterative procedure in which EOF are used to reconstruct the entire field domain. As first guess, it uses the SeaWiFS-derived daily climatological values at missing pixels and satellite observations at valid pixels. The other Level-4 dataset is the time averages of the L3 fields and includes the standard deviation and the number of observations in the monthly period of integration.</p>
Preview	
Area of Interest	Mediterranean Sea
Time range	1997-2021

Table 7. CNR Data Cube: Mediterranean Sea Surface Chlorophyll Concentration from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Mediterranean Sea Surface Chlorophyll Concentration from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations
Dataset name [datasetId]	Mediterranean Sea Surface Chlorophyll Concentration from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations [OCMEDCHLNRTL3]
Title	Chlorophyll a (chlor_a)
Description	<p>The Global Ocean Satellite monitoring and marine ecosystem study group (GOS) of the Italian National Research Council (CNR), in Rome, distributes surface chlorophyll concentration (mg m⁻³) derived from multi-sensor (MODIS-AQUA, NOAA20-VIIRS, NPP-VIIRS, and Sentinel3A-OLCI at 300m of resolution) (at 1 km resolution) and Sentinel3A-OLCI (at high resolution, 300m) Rrs spectra. Chlorophyll datasets are obtained by means of the Mediterranean Ocean Colour regional algorithms: an updated version of the MedOC4 (Case 1 waters, Volpe et al., 2019, with new coefficients) and AD4 (Case 2 waters, Berthon and Zibordi, 2004). Discrimination between the two water types is performed by comparing the satellite spectrum at pixel-by-pixel level with the average water type spectral signature from in situ measurements for both water types. Reference insitu dataset is MedBiOp (Volpe et al., 2019) where pure Case II spectra are selected using a k-mean cluster analysis (Melin et al., 2015). Merging of Case 1 and Case 2 information is performed estimating the Mahalanobis distance between the observed and reference spectra and using it as weight for the final merged value. This product identifies the average chlorophyll content of the surface layer as defined by the first optical depth (roughly one fifth of the euphotic depth). For multi-sensor observations, single sensor Rrs fields are band-shifted, over the SeaWiFS native bands (using the QAAv6 model, Lee et al., 2002) and merged with a technique aimed at smoothing the differences among different sensors. The current day data temporal consistency is evaluated as Quality Index (QI):</p> $QI = \frac{\text{CurrentDataPixel} - \text{ClimatologyDataPixel}}{\text{STDDataPixel}}$ <p>where QI is the difference between current data and the relevant climatological field as a signed multiple of climatological standard deviations (STDDataPixel).</p>
Preview	
Area of Interest	Mediterranean Sea
Time range	from 2016-04-25 to present

Table 8. CNR Data Cube: Mediterranean Sea Monthly and Daily Reprocessed Surface Chlorophyll Concentration from Multi Satellite observations + SeaWiFS daily climatology.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Mediterranean Sea Monthly and Daily Reprocessed Surface Chlorophyll Concentration from Multi Satellite observations + SeaWiFS daily climatology
Dataset name [datasetId]	Mediterranean Sea Monthly and Daily Reprocessed Surface Chlorophyll Concentration from Multi Satellite observations + SeaWiFS daily climatology [OCMEDCHLL4]
Title	Chlorophyll a (chlor_a)
Description	<p>The Global Ocean Satellite monitoring and marine ecosystem study group (GOS) of the Italian National Research Council (CNR), in Rome, distributes Level-4 product including the daily interpolated chlorophyll field with no data voids starting from the multi-sensor (MODIS-Aqua, NOAA-20-VIIRS, NPP-VIIRS, Sentinel3A-OLCI), the monthly averaged chlorophyll concentration for the multi-sensor and climatological fields, all at 1 km resolution. Chlorophyll field are obtained by means of the Mediterranean regional algorithms: an updated version of the MedOC4 (Case 1 waters, Volpe et al., 2019, with new coefficients) and AD4 (Case 2 waters, Berthon and Zibordi, 2004). Discrimination between the two water types is performed by comparing the satellite spectrum with the average water type spectral signature from in situ measurements for both water types. Reference insitu dataset is MedBiOp (Volpe et al., 2019) where pure Case II spectra are selected using a k-mean cluster analysis (Melin et al., 2015). Merging of Case I and Case II information is performed estimating the Mahalanobis distance between the observed and reference spectra and using it as weight for the final merged value. The interpolated gap-free Level-4 Chl concentration is estimated by means of a modified version of the DINEOF algorithm by GOS (Volpe et al., 2018). DINEOF is an iterative procedure in which EOF are used to reconstruct the entire field domain. As first guess, it uses the SeaWiFS-derived daily climatological values at missing pixels and satellite observations at valid pixels. Monthly Level-4 dataset is the time averages of the L3 fields and includes the standard deviation and the number of observations in the monthly period of integration. SeaWiFS daily climatology provides reference for the calculation of Quality Indices (QI) for Chl observations.</p>
Preview	
Area of Interest	Mediterranean Sea
Time range	from 1997-09-04 to present

Table 9. CNR Data Cube: Mediterranean Sea Reprocessed Surface Chlorophyll Concentration and Phytoplankton Functional Types from Multi Satellite observations.

Title	Description
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Data Cube	Mediterranean Sea Reprocessed Surface Chlorophyll Concentration and Phytoplankton Functional Types from Multi Satellite observations
Datasets	Chl-a, PSC (Phytoplankton Sizes Class Types), PFT (Phytoplankton Functional Types)
Title	Mediterranean Sea Reprocessed Surface Chlorophyll Concentration and Phytoplankton Functional Types from Multi Satellite observations
Description	<p>The Global Ocean Satellite monitoring and marine ecosystem study group (GOS) of the Italian National Research Council (CNR) in Rome distributes reprocessed surface chlorophyll concentration (Chl) and phytoplankton functional types (PFT). Input Rrs multi-sensor (MODIS-AQUA, NOAA20-VIIRS, NPP-VIIRS, Sentinel3A-OLCI) spectra at the state-of-the-art algorithms for multi-sensor merging. Single sensor Rrs fields are band-shifted, over the SeaWiFS native bands (using the QAAv6 model, Lee et al., 2002) and merged. Reprocessed (multi-year) products are consistent and homogeneous in terms of format, algorithms and processing software. Chl is obtained by means of the Mediterranean regional algorithms: an updated version of the MedOC4 (Volpe et al., 2019) and AD4 (Berthon and Zibordi, 2004). Discrimination between the two water types is performed by comparing the satellite spectrum with the average spectrum from in situ measurements. Reference insitu dataset is MedBiOp (Volpe et al., 2019) where Case II spectra are selected with a k-mean cluster analysis (Melin et al., 2015). Merging of Case I and Case II information is performed estimating the Mahalanobis distance between observed and reference spectra and using it as weight for the final value. The PFT provides estimates of Chl concentration of 9 phytoplankton groups: Micro, Nano, Pico, Diato, Dino, Crypto, Hapto, Green and Prokar. Micro consists of Diato and Dino, Nano includes Crypto and Hapto and Pico is referred to Green and Prokar with the adjustment of Brewin et al. (2010) in the ultra-oligotrophic water for Pico and Nano. These classes are estimated via empirical regional functions, correlating Chl concentration with each in-situ PFT fraction computed by a regional diagnostic pigment analysis (Di Cicco et al. 2017).</p>
Preview	
Area of Interest	Mediterranean Sea
Time range	2010-2021

Table 10. CNR Data Cube: Mediterranean Sea Monthly Attenuation Coefficient at 490nm from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Mediterranean Sea Monthly Attenuation Coefficient at 490nm from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations
Datasets	KD490
Title	Mediterranean Sea Monthly Attenuation Coefficient at 490nm from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations

Description	<p>The Global Ocean Satellite monitoring and marine ecosystem study group (GOS) of the Italian National Research Council (CNR), in Rome operationally produces Level-4 product includes monthly averaged datasets of the diffuse attenuation coefficient of light at 490 nm (Kd490) for multi-sensor (MODIS-AQUA, NOAA20-VIIRS, NPP-VIIRS, Sentinel3A-OLCI at 300m of resolution) (at 1 km resolution) and Sentinel3A-OLCI observations (at 300m resolution). Kd490 is the diffuse attenuation coefficient of light at 490 nm, and is a measure of the turbidity of the water column, i.e., how visible light in the blue-green region of the spectrum penetrates the water column. It is directly related to the presence of absorbing and scattering matter in the water column and is estimated through the ratio between Rrs at 490 and 555 nm. For the multi-sensor dataset, single sensor Rrs fields are band-shifted, over the SeaWiFS native bands (using the QAAv6 model, Lee et al., 2002) and merged with a technique aimed at smoothing the differences among different sensors. This technique is developed by the GOS. The QAA allows the inversion of the radiative transfer equations to compute the Inherent Optical Properties. Level-4 product includes monthly averages along with the standard deviation and the number of observations in the period of integration.</p>
Preview	
Area of Interest	Mediterranean Sea
Time range	2017-2021

Table 11. CNR Data Cube: Mediterranean Sea Remote Sensing Reflectances and Attenuation Coefficient at 490nm from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Mediterranean Sea Remote Sensing Reflectances and Attenuation Coefficient at 490nm from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations
Dataset name [datasetId]	Mediterranean Sea Remote Sensing Reflectances and Attenuation Coefficient at 490nm from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations [OCMEDNRTAPH443, OCMEDNRTBBP443, OCMEDNRTKD490]
Title	Mediterranean Sea Remote Sensing Reflectances and Attenuation Coefficient at 490nm from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 OLCI observations
Description	<p>The Global Ocean Satellite monitoring and marine ecosystem study group (GOS) of the Italian National Research Council (CNR), in Rome, distributes Remote Sensing Reflectances (Rrs), and diffuse attenuation coefficient of light at 490 nm (kd490) for multi-sensor (MODIS-AQUA, NOAA20-VIIRS, NPP-VIIRS, Sentinel3A-OLCI at 300m of resolution) (at 1 km resolution) and Sentinel3A-OLCI observations (at 300m resolution). Exclusively for multi-sensor also the absorption of phytoplankton (aph443), Gelbstoff material (adg443), and the particulate backscattering (bbp443) coefficients at 443 nm are provided. Rrs is defined as the ratio of upwelling radiance and downwelling irradiance at any wavelength (412, 443, 490, 555, and 670 nm for multi-sensor, and 400, 412, 443, 490, 510, 560, 620, 665, 674, 681 and 709 nm for OLCI) and can also be expressed as the ratio of normalized water leaving</p>

	<p>Radiance (nLw) and the extra-terrestrial solar irradiance (F0). Kd490 is defined as the diffuse attenuation coefficient of light at 490 nm, and is a measure of the turbidity of the water column. It is related to the presence of scattering particles via the ratio between Rrs at 490 and 555 nm (490 and 560 nm for OLCI). For multi-sensor observations Kd490 is achieved via Mediterranean regional algorithm developed by GOS on the basis of MedBiOp in situ dataset (Volpe et al., 2019). The current day data temporal consistency is evaluated as Quality Index (QI): $QI = \frac{\text{CurrentDataPixel} - \text{ClimatologyDataPixel}}{\text{STDDDataPixel}}$ where QI is the difference between current data and the relevant climatological field as a signed multiple of climatological standard deviations (STDDDataPixel). Inherent Optical Properties (aph443, adg443 and bbb443 at 443nm) are derived via QAAv6 model.</p>
Preview	
Area of Interest	Mediterranean Sea
Time range	from 2016-04-25 to present

3.2 INGV Data Cube resources

Table 12. INGV Data Cube: MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA (MODIS Level 1B Calibrated Radiances - 1km).

Title	Description
Data Cube	MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA
Datasets	MXD21KM
Title	MODIS Level 1B Calibrated Radiances - 1km
Description	<p>The MODIS Level-1B data set contains calibrated and geolocated at-aperture radiances for 36 discrete bands located in the 0.4 μm to 14.4 μm region of the electromagnetic spectrum. These data are generated from MODIS Level-1A scans of raw radiance, and in the process are converted to geophysical units of $\text{W}/(\text{m}^2 \mu\text{m sr})$. In addition, the Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) may be determined for the solar reflective bands (1-19, 26) through knowledge of the solar irradiance (e.g., determined from MODIS solar diffuser data, and from the target illumination geometry). Additional data are provided including quality flags, error estimates and calibration data.</p> <p>Visible, shortwave infrared, and near infrared measurements are only made during the daytime, while radiances for the thermal infrared region (bands 20-25, 27-36) are measured continuously.</p> <p>The resolution of channels 1 and 2 is 250 m, channels 3 through 7 are 500m resolution, and the rest are 1 km resolution. However, for the MODIS L1B 1 km product, the 250 m and 500 m band radiance data and their associated uncertainties have been aggregated to 1 km resolution. Thus, the entire channel data set is referenced to the same spatial and geolocation scales. Separate L1B products are available for just the 250 m channels</p>

	<p>(MOD02QKM) and the 500 m channels (MOD02HKM) that preserve the original resolution of the data.</p> <p>Spatial resolution for pixels at nadir is 1 km, degrading to 4.8 km in the along-scan direction at the scan extremes. However, thanks to the overlapping of consecutive swaths and the respective pixels there, the resulting resolution at the scan extremes is about 2 km. A 55-degree scanning pattern at the EOS orbit of 705 km results in a 2330 km orbital swath width with global coverage every one to two days. A single MODIS Level-1B granule will nominally contain a scene built from 203 scans (or swaths) sampled 1354 times in the cross-track direction, corresponding to approximately 5 minutes' worth of data. Since an individual MODIS scan (or swath) will contain 10 along-track spatial elements, the scene will be composed of 1354 by 2030 pixels, resulting in a spatial coverage of 2330 km by 2030 km. Due to the MODIS scan geometry, there will be increasing overlap occurring beyond about a 25-degree scan angle.</p> <p>Users requiring the full-resolution geolocation and solar/satellite geometry can obtain the separate MODIS Level-1 Geolocation product (MOD03) from LAADS.</p>
<p>Preview</p>	
<p>Area of Interest</p>	<p>Raikoke - Curili Islands Etna - Italy Ulawun - Papua New Guinea Ubinas - Chile Anak Krakatau - Indonesia Taal - Philippines Sinabung - Indonesia Ambae - Vanuatu Island La Soufrière Thule, Groenlandia</p>
<p>Time range</p>	<p>2016 - present</p>

Table 13. INGV Data Cube: MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA (MOD03 - Geolocation - 1km).

Title	Description
Data Cube	MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA
Datasets	MXD03
Title	MOD03 - Geolocation - 1km
Description	The MOD03 product includes the geolocation fields that are calculated for each 1 km MODIS Instantaneous Field of Views (IFOV) for all orbits daily. The locations and ancillary information correspond to the intersection of the centers of each IFOV from 10 detectors in an ideal 1 km band on the Earth's surface. A digital terrain model is

	<p>used to model the Earth's surface. The main inputs are the spacecraft attitude and orbit, the instrument telemetry and the digital elevation model. The geolocation fields include geodetic Latitude, Longitude, surface height above the geoid, solar zenith and azimuth angles, satellite zenith and azimuth angles, and a land/sea mask for each 1 km sample. Additional information is included in the header to enable the calculation of the approximate location of the center of the detectors for any of the 36 MODIS bands. This product is used as input by a large number of subsequent MODIS products, particularly those produced by the Land team.</p>
<p>Preview</p>	
<p>Area of Interest</p>	<p>Raikoke - Curili Islands Etna – Italy Ulawun - Papua New Guinea Ubinas – Chile Anak Krakatau – Indonesia Taal – Philippines Sinabung – Indonesia Ambae - Vanuatu Island La Soufrière Thule, Groenlandia</p>
<p>Time range</p>	<p>2016 - present</p>

Table 14 INGV Data Cube: MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA (MXD04_L2 – MODIS Aerosol 5-Min L2 Swath 10km).

Title	Description
<p>Data Cube</p>	<p>MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA</p>
<p>Datasets</p>	<p>MXD04_L2</p>
<p>Title</p>	<p>MXD04_L2 – MODIS Aerosol 5-Min L2 Swath 10km</p>
<p>Description</p>	<p>The MODIS Aerosol Product monitors the ambient aerosol optical thickness over the oceans globally and over a portion of the continents. Further, the aerosol size distribution is derived over the oceans, and the aerosol type is derived over the continents. Daily Level-2 data are produced at the spatial resolution of a 10x10 km pixel array (at nadir).</p> <p>Prior to MODIS, satellite measurements were limited to reflectance measurements in one (GOES, METEOSAT) or two (AVHRR) channels. There was no real attempt to retrieve aerosol content over land on a global scale. Algorithms had been developed for use only over dark vegetation. The blue channel on MODIS, not present on AVHRR, offers the possibility to extend the derivation of optical thickness over land to additional surfaces. The algorithms use MODIS bands 1 through 7 and 20 and require prior cloud screening using MODIS data. Over the land, the dynamic aerosol models are derived from ground-based sky measurements and used in the net retrieval process.</p>

	<p>Over the ocean, three parameters that describe the aerosol loading and size distribution are retrieved. Pre-assumptions on the general structure of the size distribution are required in the inversion of MODIS data, and the volume-size distribution is described with two log-normal modes: a single mode to describe the accumulation mode particles (radius < 0.5 μm) and a single coarse mode to describe dust and/or salt particles (radius > 1.0 μm).</p> <p>The quality assurance control of these products will be based on comparison with ground stations and climatology.</p>
<p>Preview</p>	
<p>Area of Interest</p>	<p>Raikoke - Curili Islands Etna – Italy Ulawun - Papua New Guinea Ubinas – Chile Anak Krakatau – Indonesia Taal – Philippines Sinabung – Indonesia Ambae - Vanuatu Island La Soufrière Thule, Groenlandia</p>
<p>Time range</p>	<p>2016 - present</p>

Table 15. INGV Data Cube: MODIS-AQUA and MODIS-TERRA (MXD04_3K - MODIS Aerosol 5-Min L2 Swath 3km).

Title	Description
Data Cube	MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA
Datasets	MXD04_3K
Title	MXD04_3K - MODIS Aerosol 5-Min L2 Swath 3km
Description	<p>The MODIS 3 km Aerosol Product monitors the ambient aerosol optical properties (e.g., optical thickness and size distribution), mass concentration, look-up-table-derived reflected and transmitted fluxes, as well as quality assurance and other ancillary parameters, over the oceans globally and over a portion of the continents.</p> <p>With Collection 5 and earlier collections, only one aerosol product existed (MOD04_L2), at 10 km resolution, because its original aim was for climate studies, and the 10 km resolution worked well for global analyses. However, the air quality community had been requesting higher resolution data for quite some time to help resolve urban and neighbourhood air quality. Thus, in Collection 6, the Dark Target (DT) aerosol algorithm is used to create a new 3 km aerosol product (MOD04_3K).</p>

	<p>The MOD04_3K product is based on the same algorithm and using the same Look Up Tables as the standard Dark Target aerosol product. Because of finer resolution, subtle differences are made in selecting pixels for retrieval and in determining QA. The only differences between the existing 10 km algorithm and the new 3 km algorithm are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the size of the pixel arrays defining each retrieval box (6x6 retrieval boxes of 36 pixels at 0.5 km resolution for 3 km algorithm as opposed to 20x20 retrieval boxes used for 10km product). • the minimum percentage of "good" pixels required for a retrieval (a minimum of 5 pixels over ocean and 6 pixels over land, instead of a minimum of 10 pixels over ocean or 12 pixels over land). • the 10km algorithm attempts a "poor quality" retrieval when the number of available pixels after screening is small. The 3 km algorithm will not attempt a retrieval under these circumstances. This means that with the 3 km product, there will be no retrievals with a QA of 1 or 2 over land. • Other than these differences, everything else in the two products is the same. For additional details on the differences see the MODIS Atmospheres web site page on Collection 6.1 Updates. <p>Preliminary analysis indicates that the 3 km product tends to be noisier than the 10 km product. Comparisons of the global mean AOD from the two products shows that the 3 km AOD is 0.01 to 0.02 higher over land. Over ocean, it was found that there was more very low AOD with the 3 km product.</p>
Preview	
Area of Interest	Raikoke - Curili Islands Etna – Italy Ulawun - Papua New Guinea Ubinas – Chile Anak Krakatau – Indonesia Taal – Philippines Sinabung – Indonesia Ambae - Vanuatu Island La Soufrière Thule, Groenlandia
Time range	2016 - present

Table 16. INGV Data Cube: MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA (MXD05_L2 - MODIS Total Precipitable Water Vapor 5-Min L2 Swath 1km and 5km).

Title	Description
Data Cube	MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA
Datasets	MXD05_L2
Title	MXD05_L2 - MODIS Total Precipitable Water Vapor 5-Min L2 Swath 1km and 5km
Description	<p>The MODIS Precipitable Water product consists of column water vapor amounts. During the daytime, a near-infrared algorithm is applied over clear land areas of the globe and above clouds over both land and ocean. Over clear ocean areas, water vapor estimates are provided over the extended glint area. An infrared algorithm for deriving atmospheric profiles is also applied both day and night for Level-2. There are two MODIS Water Vapor data product files: MOD05_L2, containing data collected from the Terra platform; and MYD05_L2, containing data collected from the Aqua platform.</p> <p>The Level-2 data are generated at the 1-km spatial resolution of the MODIS instrument using the near-infrared algorithm during the day, and at 5 km x 5 km pixel resolution both day and night using the infrared algorithm, when at least nine FOVs are cloud-free. The infrared-derived precipitable water vapor is generated as one component of the Atmospheric Profile product (MOD07), and simply added to MOD05 for convenience. The solar retrieval algorithm relies on observations of water vapor attenuation of reflected solar radiation in the near-infrared MODIS channels so that the product is produced only over areas where there is a reflective surface in the near IR.</p> <p>The solar-column water vapor parameter is derived from the attenuation by water vapor of near-IR solar radiation. Techniques are used that employ ratios of water vapor-absorbing channels (17, 18, and 19) with the atmospheric window channels (2 and 5). The ratios partially remove the effects of variation of surface reflectance with wavelength and result in the atmospheric water vapor transmittance. The column water vapor amounts are derived from the transmittance, based on theoretical radiative transfer calculations and using look-up-table procedures. MODIS is the first space-based instrument to use near-IR bands together with the traditional IR bands to retrieve total precipitable water. Experience in this retrieval is based on the airborne visible/infrared imaging spectrometer (AVIRIS) instrument aboard the NASA Earth Resources-2 (ER-2) aircraft. Atmospheric water vapor should be determined with an accuracy of 5-10%.</p> <p>The thermal column water vapor parameter is derived by integrating the moisture profile through the atmospheric column. Other split-window methods also exist for determining water vapor. The split-window techniques use the difference in water vapor absorption that exists between channel 31 (11 μm) and channel 32 (12 μm). Data validation is conducted by comparing these data with water vapor measurements from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Agency (NOAA) National Weather Service (NWS) radiosonde network, ground-based upward-looking microwave radiometers, a ground-based GPS network, and from the AEROSOL ROBOTIC NETWORK (AERONET) ground-based sunphotometer network.</p> <p>The near-infrared total column precipitable water is very sensitive to boundary layer water vapor since it is derived from attenuation of reflected solar light from the surface. This data product is essential to understanding the hydrological cycle, aerosol properties, aerosol-cloud interactions, energy budget, and climate. Of particular interest is the collection of water vapor data above cirrus cloudiness, which has important applications to climate studies.</p>
Preview	

<p>Area of Interest</p>	<p>Raikoke - Curili Islands Etna – Italy Ulawun - Papua New Guinea Ubinas – Chile Anak Krakatau – Indonesia Taal – Philippines Sinabung – Indonesia Ambae - Vanuatu Island La Soufrière Thule, Groenlandia</p>
<p>Time range</p>	<p>2016 - present</p>

Table 17. INGV Data Cube: MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA (MOD11_L2 - MODIS Land Surface Temperature/Emissivity 5-Min L2 Swath 1km).

Title	Description
Data Cube	MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA
Datasets	MXD11_L2
Title	MOD11_L2 - MODIS Land Surface Temperature/Emissivity 5-Min L2 Swath 1km
Description	<p>The Land Surface Temperature (LST) and Emissivity daily data are retrieved at 1km pixels by the generalized split-window algorithm and at 6km grids by the day/night algorithm. In the split-window algorithm, emissivities in bands 31 and 32 are estimated from land cover types, atmospheric column water vapor and lower boundary air surface temperature are separated into tractable sub-ranges for optimal retrieval. In the day/night algorithm, daytime and nighttime LSTs and surface emissivities are retrieved from pairs of day and night MODIS observations in seven TIR bands. The product consists of LSTs, quality assessment, observation time, view angles, and emissivities.</p>
Preview	

Area of Interest	<p>Raikoke - Curili Islands Etna – Italy Ulawun - Papua New Guinea Ubinas – Chile Anak Krakatau – Indonesia Taal – Philippines Sinabung – Indonesia Ambae - Vanuatu Island La Soufrière Thule, Groenlandia</p>
Time range	2016 - present

Table 18. INGV Data Cube: Sentinel-1 Unwrapped interferograms and coherence maps.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Sentinel-1 Unwrapped interferograms and coherence maps
Dataset name [datasetId]	COMET-LiCS Sentinel-1 InSAR [S1AB_interferograms_cc, S1AB_interferograms_diff pha, S1AB_interferograms_diff_unfiltered pha, S1AB_interferograms_unw]
Title	COMET-LiCS Sentinel-1 InSAR: interferograms
Description	Interferograms and coherence maps have been produced automatically using the LiCSAR processor, which builds on the Gamma SAR and Interferometry software. Interferograms have been processed in overlapping “frames” defined within COMET-LiCS.
Preview	
Area of Interest	Etna – Italy
Time range	2016 - present

Table 19. INGV Data Cube: Sentinel-3 Land Surface Temperature.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Sentinel-3 Land Surface Temperature
Dataset name [datasetId]	Sentinel-3A LST (NRT) [S3A_SL_2_LST____NRT_LST_K, vr_S3B_SL_2_LST____NRT_LST_K]
Title	Sentinel-3 Land Surface Temperature
Description	Sentinel-3A Land Surface Temperature [°C] in cloud Optimised Geotiff data format available in the AWS Open Data Registry
Preview	
Area of Interest	Global
Time range	2020 - present

Table 20. INGV Data Cube: Sentinel-3 Aerosol Optical Depth.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Sentinel-3 Aerosol Optical Depth
Dataset name [datasetId]	Sentinel-3A AOD (NRT) [S3A_SL_2_AOD____NRT_AOD_550 S3A_SL_2_AOD____NRT_AOD_QUALITY_FLAGS S3B_SL_2_AOD____NRT_AOD_550 S3B_SL_2_AOD____NRT_AOD_QUALITY_FLAGS]
Title	Sentinel-3 Aerosol Optical Depth
Description	Sentinel-3A Aerosol Optical Depth in cloud Optimised Geotiff data format available in the AWS Open Data Registry
Preview	

Area of Interest	Global
Time range	2020 - present

Table 21. INGV Data Cube: Sentinel-3 Top of Atmosphere Radiances and Brightness Temperature.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Sentinel-3 Top of Atmosphere Radiances and Brightness Temperature
Dataset name [datasetId]	Sentinel-3A: OLCI L1 EFR (NRT) [vr_S3A_OL_1_EFR____NRT_RGB, vr_S3B_OL_1_EFR____NRT_RGB]
Title	Sentinel-3 Top of Atmosphere Radiances and Brightness Temperature
Description	Sentinel-3A Top of Atmosphere Radiances and Brightness Temperature in cloud Optimised Geotiff data format available in the AWS Open Data Registry
Preview	
Area of Interest	Global
Time range	2020 - present

Table 22. INGV Data Cube: Tandem X (DEM 90m).

Title	Description
Data Cube	Tandem X (DEM 90m)
Dataset name [datasetId]	TANDEM-X[TANDEM-X]
Title	TanDEM-X
Description	TDM90 Elevation (DEM): The DEM elevation values represent the ellipsoidal heights relative to the WGS84 ellipsoid in the WGS84-G1150 datum.
Preview	

Area of Interest	<p>Raikoke - Curili Islands Etna – Italy Ulawun - Papua New Guinea Ubinas – Chile Anak Krakatau – Indonesia Taal – Philippines Sinabung – Indonesia Ambae - Vanuatu Island La Soufrière Thule, Groenlandia</p>

Table 23. INGV Data Cube: SRTM (DEM 30 m).

Title	Description
Data Cube	SRMT (DEM 30 m)
Dataset name [datasetId]	SRTM XSAR Digital Elevation Model (DEM) [SRTM]
Title	SRTM XSAR Digital Elevation Model (DEM)
Description	<p>The SRTM data sets result from a collaborative effort by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and the National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency (NGA - previously known as the National Imagery and Mapping Agency, or NIMA), as well as the participation of the German and Italian space agencies, to generate a near-global digital elevation model (DEM) of the Earth using radar interferometry. The SRTM instrument consisted of the Spaceborne Imaging Radar-C (SIR-C) hardware set modified with a Space Station-derived mast and additional antennae to form an interferometer with a 60 meter long baseline. A description of the SRTM mission can be found in Farr and Kobrick (2000). Synthetic aperture radars are side-looking instruments and acquire data along continuous swaths. The SRTM swaths extended from about 30 degrees off-nadir to about 58 degrees off-nadir from an altitude of 233 km, and thus were about 225 km wide. During the data flight the instrument was operated at all times the orbiter was over land and about 1000 individual swaths were acquired over the ten days of mapping operations. Length of the acquired swaths range from a few hundred to several thousand km. Each individual data acquisition is referred to as a "data take."</p>
Preview	

Area of Interest	Raikoke - Curili Islands Etna – Italy Ulawun - Papua New Guinea Ubinas – Chile Anak Krakatau – Indonesia Taal – Philippines Sinabung – Indonesia Ambae - Vanuatu Island La Soufrière Thule, Groenlandia

3.3 UiO Data Cube resources

Table 24. UiO Data Cube: CAMS European air quality forecasts.

Title	Description
Data Cube	CAMS European air quality forecasts
Datasets	Ammonia, carbon_monoxide, nitrogen_dioxide, nitrogen_monoxide, non_methane_vocs, ozone, particulate_matter_10um, particulate_matter_2.5um, peroxyacyl_nitrates, residential_elementary_carbon, secondary_inorganic_aerosol, sulphur_dioxide, total_elementary_carbon
Title	CAMS European air quality forecasts
Description	<p>This dataset provides daily air quality analyses and forecasts for Europe.</p> <p>CAMS produces specific daily air quality analyses and forecasts for the European domain at significantly higher spatial resolution (0.1 degrees, approx. 10km) than is available from the global analyses and forecasts. The production is based on an ensemble of nine air quality forecasting systems across Europe. A median ensemble is calculated from individual outputs, since ensemble products yield on average better performance than the individual model products. The spread between the nine models is used to provide an estimate of the forecast uncertainty. The analysis combines model data with observations provided by the European Environment Agency (EEA) into a complete and consistent dataset using various data assimilation techniques depending upon the air-quality forecasting system used. In parallel, air quality forecasts are produced once a day for the next four days. Both the analysis and the forecast are available at hourly time steps at seven height levels.</p> <p>Note that only nitrogen monoxide, nitrogen dioxide, sulphur dioxide, ozone, PM2.5, PM10 and dust are regularly validated against in situ observations, and therefore forecasts of all other variables are unvalidated and should be considered experimental.</p>
Preview	

Area of Interest	Europe (east boundary=25.0° W, west=45.0° E, south=30.0° N, north=70.0°)
Time range	three-year rolling archive

Table 25. UiO Data Cube: UERRA regional reanalysis for Europe on single levels from 1961 to 2019.

Title	Description
Data Cube	UERRA regional reanalysis for Europe on single levels from 1961 to 2019
Datasets	snow density, snow depth water equivalent, 2m temperature, skin temperature, total precipitation, albedo, orography, total cloud cover
Title	UERRA regional reanalysis for Europe on single levels from 1961 to 2019
Description	<p>This UERRA dataset contains analyses of surface and near-surface essential climate variables from UERRA-HARMONIE and MESCAN-SURFEX systems. Forecasts up to 30 hours initialised from the analyses at 00 and 12 UTC are available only through the CDS-API (see Documentation).</p> <p>UERRA-HARMONIE is a 3-dimensional variational data assimilation system, while MESCAN-SURFEX is a complementary surface analysis system. Using the Optimal Interpolation method, MESCAN provides the best estimate of daily accumulated precipitation and six-hourly air temperature and relative humidity at 2 meters above the model topography.</p> <p>The land surface platform SURFEX is forced with downscaled forecast fields from UERRA-HARMONIE as well as MESCAN analyses. It is run offline, i.e., without feedback to the atmospheric analysis performed in MESCAN or the UERRA-HARMONIE data assimilation cycles. Using SURFEX offline allows to take full benefit of precipitation analysis and to use the more advanced physics options to better represent surface variables such as surface temperature and surface fluxes, and soil processes related to water and heat transfer in the soil and snow.</p> <p>In general, the assimilation systems are able to estimate biases between observations and to sift good-quality data from poor data. The laws of physics allow for estimates at locations where data coverage is low. The provision of estimates at each grid point in Europe for each regular output time, over a long period, always using the same format, makes reanalysis a very convenient and popular dataset to work with. The observing system has changed drastically over time, and although the assimilation system can resolve data holes, the much sparser observational networks, e.g., in the 1960s, will have an impact on the quality of analyses leading to less accurate estimates. The improvement over global reanalysis products comes with the higher horizontal resolution that allows incorporating more regional details (e.g., topography). Moreover, it enables the system even to use more observations at places with dense observation networks.</p>
Preview	

Area of Interest	Europe
Time range	January 1961 to July 2019

Table 26. UiO DataCube: Arctic regional reanalysis on single levels from 1998 to 2019.

Title	Description
Data Cube	Arctic regional reanalysis on single levels from 1998 to 2019
Datasets	albedo, snow density, surface thermal radiation downward, surface solar radiation downwards, total precipitation, 2m temperature, orography, snow depth water equivalent
Title	Arctic regional reanalysis on single levels from 1998 to 2019
Description	<p>The C3S Arctic Regional Reanalysis (CARRA) dataset contains 3-hourly analyses and hourly short-term forecasts of atmospheric and surface meteorological variables (surface and near-surface temperature, surface and top of atmosphere fluxes, precipitation, cloud, humidity, wind, pressure, snow and sea variables) at 2.5 km resolution. Additionally, forecasts up to 30 hours initialised from the analyses at 00 and 12 UTC are available.</p> <p>The dataset includes two domains. The West domain covers Greenland, the Labrador Sea, Davis Strait, Baffin Bay, Denmark Strait, Iceland, Jan Mayen, the Greenland Sea, and parts of Svalbard. The East domain covers Svalbard, Franz Josef Land, Novaya Zemlya, Barents Sea, and the Northern parts of the Norwegian Sea and Scandinavia.</p> <p>The dataset has been produced with the use of the HARMONIE-AROME state-of-the-art non-hydrostatic regional numerical weather prediction model. High resolution reanalysis for the Arctic region is particularly important because the climate change is more pronounced in the Arctic region than elsewhere in the Earth. This fact calls for a better description of this region providing additional details with respect to the global reanalyses (ERA5 for instance). The additional information is provided by the higher horizontal resolution, more local observations (from the Nordic countries and Greenland), better description of surface characteristics (high resolution satellite and physiographic data), high resolution non-hydrostatic dynamics and improved physical parameterisation of clouds and precipitation in particular.</p> <p>The inputs to CARRA reanalysis are the observations, the ERA5 global reanalysis as lateral boundary conditions and the physiographic datasets describing the surface characteristics of the model. The observation values and information about their quality are used together to constrain the reanalysis where observations are available and provide information for the data assimilation system in areas in where less observations are available.</p>
Preview	

<p>Area of Interest</p>	<p>West domain: The domain covers Greenland, Labrador Sea, Davis Strait, Baffin Bay, Denmark Strait, Iceland, Jan Mayen, Greenland Sea, and parts of Svalbard</p> <p>East domain: This domain covers Svalbard, Franz Josef Land, Novaya Zemlya, Barents Sea, and the Northern parts of the Norwegian Sea and Scandinavia</p>
<p>Time range</p>	<p>From 1998 to 2019</p>

Table 27. UiO Data Cube: ERA5-Land hourly data from 1981 to present.

Title	Description
<p>Data Cube</p>	<p>ERA5-Land hourly data from 1981 to present</p>
<p>Datasets</p>	<p>total precipitation, 2m temperature, 2m dew temperature</p>
<p>Title</p>	<p>ERA5-Land hourly data from 1981 to present</p>
<p>Description</p>	<p>ERA5-Land is a reanalysis dataset providing a consistent view of the evolution of land variables over several decades at an enhanced resolution compared to ERA5. ERA5-Land has been produced by replaying the land component of the ECMWF ERA5 climate reanalysis. Reanalysis combines model data with observations from across the world into a globally complete and consistent dataset using the laws of physics. Reanalysis produces data that goes several decades back in time, providing an accurate description of the climate of the past.</p> <p>ERA5-Land uses as input to control the simulated land fields ERA5 atmospheric variables, such as air temperature and air humidity. This is called the atmospheric forcing. Without the constraint of the atmospheric forcing, the model-based estimates can rapidly deviate from reality. Therefore, while observations are not directly used in the production of ERA5-Land, they have an indirect influence through the atmospheric forcing used to run the simulation. In addition, the input air temperature, air humidity and pressure used to run ERA5-Land are corrected to account for the altitude difference between the grid of the forcing and the higher resolution grid of ERA5-Land. This correction is called 'lapse rate correction'.</p> <p>The ERA5-Land dataset, as any other simulation, provides estimates which have some degree of uncertainty. Numerical models can only provide a more or less accurate representation of the real physical processes governing different components of the Earth System. In general, the uncertainty of model estimates grows as we go back in time, because the number of observations available to create a good quality atmospheric forcing is lower. ERA5-land parameter fields can currently be used in combination with the uncertainty of the equivalent ERA5 fields.</p> <p>The temporal and spatial resolutions of ERA5-Land makes this dataset very useful for all kind of land surface applications such as flood or drought forecasting. The temporal and spatial resolution of this dataset, the period covered in time, as well as the fixed grid used for the data distribution at any period enables decisions makers, businesses and individuals to access and use more accurate information on land states.</p>

<p>Preview</p>	
<p>Area of Interest</p>	<p>Global</p>
<p>Time range</p>	<p>From 1981 to present</p>

4 References

[D4.1] Corcho O., Gonzalez E., Garijo D., Foglini F., Trasatti E., Fouilloux A., Mantovani S., Gonçalves P. “D4.1 Data Cube Metadata Model”, RELIANCE project deliverable. May 10th 2021.

[D4.2] Mantovani S. “D4.2 Data Cubes API - Release I”, RELIANCE project deliverable. July 2021.

[D4.4] Mantovani S. “D4.4 - FAIR Data Cubes - Release I”, RELIANCE project deliverable. July 2021.